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Instruments for the natural magnetic fields registration in the city conditions: the magnetic storm indicators

In the paper application of the new instruments – the magnetic storm indicators (MSI) for the natural magnetic field registration in the city conditions has been described.

The construction of devices using fluxgate sensors allow to use MSI in various conditions and premises with the larger level of electromagnetic noises.

The description of main characteristics of MSI are shortly presented.

1.

INTRODUCTION

Necessity to make defences measure from the influence of magnetic storm (MS) in the first place dictate need for the means of its revelation in the real time scale in the industrial big city conditions with strong artificially created electromagnetic radiations and by noises, amplitude which can achieve 1... 10 T and more [2, 8, 11, 16, 19]. Till recent time was believed, what to fix MS you may only in places with comparatively quiet magnetic field, without strong industrial noises [5]. Knownly, what level of noise with the net frequency in ordinary laboratory conditions or in the urban hospitals condition and clinic can exceed the variations of natural geomagnetic field (GMF) in thousand and more time [5, 8]. Noise from electrify transport have impulse character and compose as to amplitude dozens of nT at a distance in the hundreds of metres [2, 8, 11]. The spectral structure of urban noises practically superimpose the spectra of all known signals from biological objects. The maximum of the spectrum of GMF variations generally it is necessary on the domain of approximately twenty-four hours periods, depending on the geomagnetic latitude of the observation place, with the sharp decrease in the domain of short periods. During strong MS the spectrum of geomagnetic variations shift in the domain of short periods [10, 11].

2. PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATIONS AND PROBLEME SOLVING

From the point of view of medicine and magnetobiology that fact now does not cause any more of doubts. that electromagnetic fields (EMF) of a

natural origin should be considered as one of the major ecological factors [1, 2, 8, 9, 11, 18, 20]. The presence of natural EMF in an environment is completely necessary for existence of normal ability to live, and their absence or the deficiency - results to serious negative, at times even to irreversible consequences for alive organism [1, 11, 17, 18, 20].

Our investigations [1, 3-8, 11, 14-16, 18, 20] showed the principle possibility of diagnostic magnetometers (DM) application, realized on the basis of fluxgate sensors, in the city conditions with the larger level of electromagnetic noises. Therefore in 1990 in IZMIRAN begin to creation of simple and inexpensive instruments for the equipment of medical establishments, capable visualized the process of the GMF change in real time [10-14]. As a result was created a new class of DM - the magnetic storm indicators (MSI).

Are carried out of investigations, purpose which was creation reliable and inexpensive instruments for MS revelation in the conditions with the high level of technogenic hindrances and noises, for the realization of local electromagnetic control in hospitals, clinics, in the rest zones, in residential and manufacturing premises. In the process of experimental works were created special computer programs allowing to conduct correlation analysis receivable medical and geophysical information.

Manufactured in period from 1992 to 2002 models of MSI were received small, simple in exploitation and maintenance [10, 13]. The experimental samples of a number of instruments passed clinical and laboratory tests in research centers and organisations. Accumulated the experience of various types DM and MSI application in clinic showed the principal possibility of application created magnetometrical equipment in the conditions with the larger level of technogenic electromagnetic noises [3, 5, 13]. It was shown experimentally the possibility and the necessity of MS registration in the clinic conditions [4, 8, 15, 16]. Main characteristics of created analog and digital MSI are presented below.

3. MAGNETIC STORM INDICATORS

The MSI MF-01 [10, 13] is high sensitivity analog magnetometer includes in itself two units: the magnetic measuring converter – MMC (250x80x40 mm) and the indication unit – IU (110x90x55 mm), connected between each other cable by length 10..15 m. Information about the MS intensity change, its instantaneous significance on the 6-level luminous indicator are represented. Weight of instrument is not above 1,2 kg.

The MSI MF-04 MAGIC [13] was create as a laboratory device consisting two units: MMC and IU, connected between each other cable by length 6...10 m. Information about the change of MS intensity, its instantaneous and middle significance for the 60-minute interval of time, visualized on luminous indicator of IU. For the current time indication are used built-in timer and digital display. Is provided the possibility of the MS value indication at the help of switch on the acoustic signaling and possibility of around-the-clock receivable information fixing in the real time scale at the help of analog recorder. Number of fixed by the indicator of the MS

gradation is 6. The weight of instrument is not above 3 kg.

Small-size diagnostic magnetometer - MSI MF-05 [12-14] was create as a home appliances wall-instrument. Information about the change of MS intensity, its instantanous significance, visualized on luminous indicator. Are provided the possibility of the MS value indication at the help of sound signaling and the possibility of fixing and visualize its maximal significance at the help of luminous indicator. Instrument lets around-the-clockly to fix receivable information in the real time scale at help of analog recorder. Number of MS gradations fixed by the indicator is 6. The remote magnetometer cable length is 6...10 m. Units dimensions are 160 mm (length) and 70 mm (external diameter). Weight of MSI MF-05 is not above 0.5 kg. Instrument is handy to work and MS registration in inhabited room conditions [20].

Created MSI: MF-01, MF-04 MAGIC and MF-05 successfully were used for realization electromagnetic monitoring in conditions of clinics Moscow, Yalta and Kislovodsk sityes [4-8, 13-16]. For example, MF-01, established in branch of reanimation Central Railway Hospital (CRH) No.3 of Moscow, has studied in a continuous mode more than six years. Use MSI in clinic has allowed us to produce the necessary recommendations for revealing and to treatment of the magnetodepending cardiological patients [4, 18].

By the beginning of active realization of research work on study of biotropical influence of natural and artificial EMF creation has per capita served experimental model of the Geophysical Data Logger - MSI IDL-04 [13, 21]. MSI IDL-04 is appointed for registration, storage, processing, analysis and representation of slowly changeable in real time information from eight analog sensors, as an one of which is used MMC (140x80x40 mm). IDL-04 carries out visualization of "signal-time" schedule on display, transmitting the measuring data in PC, the output of data in analog recorder, the production of the "hard copy" of display on printer, calculation and demonstration of the magnetic activity index. Instrument will realize the original algorithm of work which lets using receivable in the tempo of experiment data, to signalized about the MS, to calculate and visualize K-index of magnetic activity on base of the search, detections and the definitions of days with quiet geomagnetic situation. At the calculation of magnetic disturbance and the index of magnetic activity the registration data undergo by digital filtration. The volume of nonvolative memory lets to data accumulation during 14...113 days. The instruments weight is not above 3 kg.

At present time MSI IDL-04 already four years is used for monitoring realization and MS registration in clinic conditions (in Moscow CRH No.3), where is organized continuous service of tracking for an environmental electromagnetic conditions in real time scale, that allows to have constantly data about current magnetic field disturbance and in due time to carry out therapy of magnetosensitivity ill at the MS beginning [3, 4].

Magnetic Activity Recorder - MSI IDL.-04M [10] appear a modern model

of IDL-04. It is appointed for measurement in real time of D-component of GMF variations, for registration, accumulation, processing, analysis and the data representation of this measurements, for the arranging of monitoring works as to the investigation of surrounding environment, for arranging medical and magnetobiological researches. IDL-04M has two measuring channel for MMC connecting by cables (8...10 m). Instrument has built-in graphic indicator. Fixed magnetic field data undergo digital filtration. The volume of nonvolatile memory lets to accumulate information during 65 days. The instruments weight is not above 2 kg.

Now MSI IDL-04M during one year in Research Laboratory of Moscow Physics-Technical Institute is used successfully.

Universal Data Logger –MSI IDL-07 [13, 21] can decide a lot of scientific, research and applied problems in geophysics, to find broad application for monitoring works realization on multiparametrical research of an environment, to help of preventive measures realizations in medicine, to be applied in magnetobiological researches. On the basis of IDL-07 it is possible construction of autonomous observatories and stations for a measurement of various physical fields.

The MSI IDL-07 is functionally independent compact device of a continuous operation intended for registration, accumulation, processing, analysis, visualization and transfer to PC informations from analog sensors on 8 measuring channels. It includes IU (200x140x230 mm) and two of analog magnetometer converters MMC, which are connected accordingly to first and second measuring channels. Remaining the measuring channels can be used for connection of electrical field, pressure, humidity, temperature and other sensors, have an electrical output.

Both MMC represent highly sensitive and high-precision one-component fluxgate magnetometers, first of which (140x80x40 mm) allows to conduct measurements of GMF D-component variations in any region of Globe without additional tuning, and second MMC (60x20x20 mm) is intended for an amplitudes measurement of artificially created constant or variable magnetic fields for want of realizations of researches in coil systems, in magnetic shielded rooms and cameras, in locations and observatories.

The MMC IDL-07 realizes the following operations: visualization on the indicator of the schedule "signal - time", transfer accumulated datas through the serial port, accumulation of datas in internal memory, account and demonstrating of a magnetic activity index. The possibility of digital indication of outcomes is stipulated measurements of a magnetic field on each from magnetometric channels for want of realizations of their preliminary adjustment, calibration and for want of realizations of discrete measurements.

In a mode of long continuous work IDL-07 automatically watches current magnetic disturbances. For the notification about the fixed disturbance the MSI is supplied with the sound signalisation. For want of account of amplitude of magnetic disturbance and index of magnetic activity the datas of IDL-07 are subjected of digital filtration. The main parameters and

operational modes of IDL-07 are selected with the help of functional buttons located on forward board of IU, agrees the menu or can be made by the program depending on the user's problems. The IU is supplied with the liquid-crystal graphics display with sizes of 320 x 240 points. For want of realizations long continuous measurements with IDL-07 the power-down mode is stipulated. It is appointed for the carrying out of monitoring works as to the investigation of surrounding environment, for execution of medical and magnetobiological researches. On the basis of instrument is possible of autonomous stations and observatory construction.

Magnetic Activity Recorder - MSI IDL-09 [10] is appointed for detection and the indications of the MS amplitude in any regions of Globe in the real time scale, for measurement, registration, logging, analysis and data representation about the magnetic field change. The volume of nonvolatile memory lets to accumulate the information during 3...5 days. Instrument has analog output and equipped by built-in digital (graphic) display.

The power supply of all devices is carried out as from storage battery by voltage 9...12V DC or from network AC by standard network adapter. The more detailed characteristics of the created devices are given in [10, 13, 21].

4. **CONCLUSIONS**

In IZMIRAN during last 10 years experimental samples of DM on base of the one component fluxgate sensor are created, which main advantages are: economy, small sizes and weight, and also rather low cost. Our researches have shown, that these devices can be used for measurement of natural GMF variations and magnetic fields created by artificial sources in any premises in conditions of industrial city. For use in the field of medicine and magnetobiology the new class of devices - magnetic storm indicators is created. MSI allow to determine and visualize of MS amplitude in any area of Globe in real time scale and by that to help practical medicine in rendering the duly help to the people subject to heightened sensibility to changes of a magnetic field.

New generation of digital MSI IDL-04, IDL-07 and IDL-09 allow to fix physical fields and processes, to connect the analog sensors, placed in city, as basic meteorological parameters (temperature and humidity of air, atmospheric pressure, speed of a wind etc.), and geophysical parameters (electrical and magnetic components of a natural field). At the same time with magnetometrical information such devices allow the information to spend of multiparametrical monitoring work on research of an environment, it is more effective visualize occurring processes at realization of magnetobiological researches.

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